

Intelligently Controlled Spy Vehicle

Joseph Afolabi^{1*} & Mr. Arumugam Ganesan²

¹Student, Level-3 Diploma in Engineering, ²Faculty In-Charge, ^{1,2}ASTI Academy, Dubai, UAE.
Correspondence to (Joseph Afolabi) - A3092015@student.astiacademy.ac.ae*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46759/IIJSR.2022.6401>

Copyright © 2022 Joseph Afolabi. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Article Received: 07 August 2022

Article Accepted: 19 October 2022

Article Published: 07 December 2022

ABSTRACT

This venture expects to construct and program a multi-layered wisely control spy vehicle utilizing collecting strategies and python Programming. The Robot has a cutting-edge regulator that performs concurrent undertakings like low inertness top quality imaging and simulated intelligence figuring. Each wheel utilized in the Robot is a Mecanum wheel made of 12 rollers. The Mecanum wheel is an omnidirectional wheel intended for land vehicles to work toward any path. Contrasted with slip steers, Mecanum wheels have no extra erosion while going because of the more modest contact region. This Robot likewise comprises of a first-individual (FPV) camera, unequivocally constrained by the gimbal's yaw and pitch development. The gimbal's yaw uses a battery-worked gadget to address unexpected wobbles in the FPV Camera during movement with the assistance of engines and sensors. As found in the Figure underneath, the Robot likewise comprises of an improvised blaster, utilizing Drove lights to frame

Keywords: Robot; Wheel; Gimbal; Mecanum; Battery; Control; Spy vehicle, FPV Camera.

1. INTRODUCTION

insightfully control spy vehicle: Mechanical technology manages the plan, development, activity, and utilization of robots, as well as PC frameworks for their control, tangible criticism, and data handling. They are likewise utilized for occupations which are excessively grimy, risky or dull to be reasonable for people. Relatively these innovations are utilized to foster machines that can fill in for people and repeat human activities. PWM is a tweak cycle or strategy utilized in most correspondence frameworks for encoding the plentifulness of a sign solidly into a heartbeat width or term of another sign, normally a transporter signal, for transmission. IR Sensor Module Circuit IR sensor is a viral sensor, which is utilized in numerous applications in hardware, similar to it is utilized in a Controller framework, Movement identifier, Robotronics, Item Counter, Line supporter Robots, Cautions, and so on. It does this by either discharging or recognizing infrared radiation. Infrared sensors are likewise equipped for estimating the intensity being radiated by an item and recognizing movement.

The Competitors, acquiring information on about the keenly control spy vehicle course, will be ready to well work in implanted framework. Our accreditation course and preparing by the talented individuals assists with further developing abilities to create with qualified coaches.

1.1. Scope of the Paper

This paper scope is to embrace this field of this science, embrace the new world of AI and make it possible for AI robots to assist humans and optimise this technology as required.

2. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The point of this paper is to construct and program a diverse S1 Burglarize ace utilizing collecting strategies and Scratch Programming. The robot will comprise of an innovative regulator that performs synchronous errands like low inertness superior quality imaging and man-made intelligence processing. Each wheel utilized in the robot is a

Mecanum wheel made of 12 rollers. The Mecanum wheel is an omnidirectional wheel plan for land vehicles to work toward any path. In contrast with slide steers, Mecanum wheels have no extra grating while turning, because of more modest contact region. This robot comprises of a first-individual view (FPV) camera, which is unequivocally constrained by the gimbal's yaw and pitch development. The gimbal's yaw uses a battery-worked gadget to address unexpected wobbles in the FPV Camera during movement, with the assistance of engines and sensors. As found in Figures above, the robot comprises of a shoddy blaster, utilizing Drove lights frame its direction. The robot's frame is cushioned with wise love boards that distinguish Infrared and gel dabs, making it receptive to an assault. Utilizing Scratch, I was able to investigate the lighting impacts, gimbal developments and substantially more.

The Deny expert will comprise of 46 parts, six Heartbeat Width Adjustment (PWM) and other custom adornments. A portion of the determinations will incorporate 2560 by 1440 still photograph goal, 16 Mbps video bitrate, 5 Super Pixels, 1000 Rpm of Engine Rotational Speed, 19 W of Greatest Result Power, FOC Driver, shut circle Speed Control, 2400 Mah Battery Limit, Lipo 3S Battery Type, 28 W Evaluated Voltage, 5.9-6.8 Mm GEI Globule Breadth and IOs Loot ace application. Below are diagrams format for working mechanisms for the essential parts of the robot.

3. MATERIALS

The goal of my papers is to bring more people to create robots that can help Is used to connect the wires and the robot head, and all the parts of the robot in the future.

Chasis Cover Attached to the Chassis Middle Frame Before Delivery

Is used to connect the wires and the robot head, and all the parts of the robot.

Mecanum-Rader

It is specially used for the tires.

Deck line Guide

It is to help the titles and state street.

Mecanum wheel Damping ring

This is what you use for the tries.

Left- threaded Inner HUB

It is used for the four tires.

Left- threaded outer Hub

This is what we use in the tires to put everything in order.

Mecanum Wheel Roller

This is what we use for all tires

Blaster (Gel Bead Container included)

This item is connected to the robot head. We then put the bullets into a container Connected to the Robot's head.

M3508I Brushless Motor and ESC

We connected it to the tires and passed it through the wires that relate to the board.

Damping Ring Bracket

It is put inside the tire to manage vibration and bad road effects on stability.

Gimbal

Controls the **gimbal's** yaw and works with the pitch motor to help **aim and stabilise** the **Blaster**. Pitch Motor Controls the gimbal's pitch and works with the yaw motor to assist the **Blaster** aim at **its target** and to achieve stabilisation.

Camera

Designed for the S1 robot, the S1 Camera features a 5-megapixel 1/4-inch sensor and a 120° FOV, allowing users to control the S1 from a first-person perspective.

Front Axle Cover

It is what you put in front of the robot.

Front Axle Module Base

It is what you put in front of the robot.

Chassis Cabin Cover

This is what they use to cover the back of the wires.

Intelligent Controller

This device is what we use to connect to the app; when you put on the WiFi it automatically connects to the app that is what is useful.

Speaker

The S1 speaker is compatible with 2.5mm devices rated at 2W. The speaker offers users a more immersive experience with sound effects. B. When S1 fires her Another S1 attacks Gel Beads.

Chassis Middle Frame (Intelligent Battery included)

We put the battery inside the place so that Robot can come on when you put the battery.

Hit Detector

The hit detector helps the Robot it can move to a place and helps the robot head to move faster, and it can sense people's movements.

Intelligent Battery Charger

The **intelligent battery** has a capacity of **2400mAh**, a voltage of **10.8V**, and **various** power management functions. Battery Level **Indicator: LED indicates** the current battery level.

Charging the Intelligent Battery

The S1 Battery Charger is **used to charge the S1's battery**. Lift the cover **of the Battery Charger** and insert the **Intelligent Battery**. Connect the charger to a **wall outlet (100-240V, 50/60Hz)**.

Chassis Left Armor

It is What we put at the left and pasture the wire and connect to the board.

Chassis Right Armor

This is what you'll place on the right side to graze the wires and connect to the board.

Chassis Front Armor

The one that attaches to the front to feed the wires and connect to the board.

Appendix - A

Use these Rob master S1 led looping templates in your next

Rob master S1 Python program.

robot=robot CTRL

gimbal=gimbal CTRL

chassis=chassis CTRL

media=media CTRL

armor=armor CTRL

led=led CTRL

define=medicine

led_set_top_bottom=(

led_ctrl.set_top_led,

led_ctrl.set_bottom_led)

gun_led_on_off=(

led_ctrl.gun_led_off,

led.gun_led_on)

define_armor_all=rm_define.armor_all

define_armor_top_bottom_all=(

rm_define.armor_top_all,

rm_define.armor_bottom_all)

define_armor_top_right_left=(

rm_define.armor_top_right,

rm_define.armor_top_left)

define_armor_bottom_right_left=(

rm_define.armor_bottom_right,

rm_define.armor_bottom_left)

define_armor_bottom_front_back=(

rm_define.armor_bottom_front,

rm_define.armor_bottom_back)

define_effect=(

rm_define.effect_always_off,

rm_define.effect_always_on,

```
rm_define.effect_flash,
rm_define.effect_breath,
rm_define.effect_marquee)
```

```
l1,l2,x,y=0,255,1,-1
delay1, delay2,seconds=.1,.2,1
RGB_COLOURS=[
[l1,l2,l2], # RGB Cyan
[l2,l1,l2], # RGB Pink
[l1,l2,l2], # RGB Cyan
[l2,l1,l2], # RGB Pink
[l1,l2,l2], # RGB Cyan
```

Appendix - B

```
RGB_RY=[
[] # empty list box
[l2,l1,l1], # RGB Red
[l2,l2,l1], # RGB Yellow
RGB_RYBG=[
[], # empty list box
[l2,l1,l1], # RGB Red
[l2,l2,l1], # RGB Yellow
[l1,l1,l2], # RGB Blue
[l1,l2,l1], # RGB Green
[l2,l1,l1], # RGB Red
[l2,l2,l1], # RGB Yellow
[l1,l1,l2], # RGB Blue
[l1,l2,l1], # RGB Green
]
```

```
def start():
```

Function 1:

```
def rgb_single_red_yellow_forward ():
while True:
gun_led_on_off[x]()
for i in range(8):
led_set_top_bottom[0](define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],
RGB_RY[i+1][0],RGB_RY[i+1][1],RGB_RY[i+1][2],define_effect[0])
```

```
led.set_single_led(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],[i+1],define_effect[1])
led_set_top_bottom[1](define_armor_top_bottom_all[1],
RGB_RY[i+1][0],RGB_RY[i+1][1],RGB_RY[i+1][2],define_effect[1])
time.sleep(delay1);gun_led_on_off[11]()
```

Function 2:

```
def rgb_single_blue_green_forward():
while True:
gun_led_on_off[x]()
for i in range(8):
led_set_top_bottom[0](define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],
RGB_BG[i+1][0],RGB_BG[i+1][1],RGB_BG[i+1][2],define_effect[0])
led.set_single_led(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],[i+1],define_effect[1])
led_set_top_bottom[1](define_armor_top_bottom_all[1],
RGB_BG[i+1][0],RGB_BG[i+1][1],RGB_BG[i+1][2],define effect[1])
time. Sleep(delay1);gun_led_on_off[11]()
```

Function 3:

```
def rgb_single_pink_cyan_forward():
while True:
gun_led_on_off[x]()
for i in range (8):
led_set_top_bottom[0]
(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],
RGB_PC[i+1][0], RGB_PC[i+1][1],RGB_PC[i+1][2],define effect[0])
led.set_single_led(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],[i+1],define_effect[1])
led_set_top_bottom[1](define_armor_top_bottom_all[1],
RGB_PC[i+1][0],RGB_PC[i+1][1],RGB_PC[i+1][2],define_effect[1])
time.sleep(delay1);gun_led_on_off[11]()
```

Function 4:

```
def rgb_single_red_yellow_reverse():
while True:
gun_led_on_off[x]()
for i in range(8,l1,y):
led_set_top_bottom[0](define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],
RGB_RY[i][0],RGB_RY[i][1],RGB_RY[i][2],define_effect[0])
led.set_single_led(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],[i],define_effect[1])
led_set_top_bottom[1](define_armor_top_bottom_all[1],
RGB_RY[i][0],RGB_RY[i][1],RGB_RY[i][2],define_effect[1])
time.sleep(delay1);gun_led_on_off[11]()
```

Function 5:

```
def rgb_single_blue_green_reverse():
while True:
```

```
gun_led_on_off[x]()
for i in range(8,11,y):
led_set_top_bottom[0](define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],
RGB_BG[i][0],RGB_BG[i][1],RGB_BG[i][2],define_effect[0])
led.set_single_led(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],[i],define_effect[1])
led_set_top_bottom[1](define_armor_top_bottom_all[1],
RGB_BG[i][0],RGB_BG[i][1],RGB_BG[i][2],define_effect[1])
time.sleep(delay1);gun_led_on_off[11]()
```

Function 6:

```
def rgb_single_pink_cyan_reverse():
```

```
while True:
```

```
gun_led_on_off[x]()
```

```
RGB_YR=[
```

```
[], # empty list box
```

```
[12,12,11], # RGB Yellow
```

```
[12,11,11], # RGB Red
```

```
[12,12,11], # RGB Yellow
```

```
[12,11,11], # RGB Red
```

```
[12,12,11], # RGB Yellow
```

```
[12,11,11], # RGB Red
```

```
[12,12,11], # RGB Yellow
```

```
[12,11,11], # RGB Red
```

```
]
```

```
RGB_BG=[
```

```
[], # empty list box
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
]
```

```
RGB_GB=[
```

```
[], # empty list box
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
```

```
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
```

```
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
[11,12,11], # RGB Green
[11,11,12], # RGB Blue
RGB_PC=[
[], # empty list box
[12,11,12], # RGB Pink
[11,12,12], # RGB Cyan
[12,11,12], # RGB Pink

RGB_CP= [
[], # empty list box
[11,12,12], # RGB Cyan
[12,11,12], # RGB Pink

[11,12,12], # RGB Cyan
[12,11,12], # RGB Pink
[11,12,12], # RGB Cyan
[12,11,12], # RGB Pink
[11,12,12], # RGB Cyan
[12,11,12], # RGB Pink

for i in range(8,11,y):
led_set_top_bottom[0](define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],
RGB_PC[i][0],RGB_PC[i][1],RGB_PC[i][2],define_effect[0])
led.set_single_led(define_armor_top_bottom_all[0],[i],define_effect[1])
led_set_top_bottom[1](define_armor_top_bottom_all[1],
RGB_PC[i][0],RGB_PC[i][1],RGB_PC[i][2],define_effect[1])
time.sleep(delay1);gun_led_on_off[11]()
```

Appendix - C

4. CONCLUSION

I have successfully implemented the working of the wireless video surveillance robot controlled using an android mobile device. The android application uses wireless Bluetooth technology to control the Robot. Even the real-time video feed is successfully achieved using WiFi technology.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

References

- [1] Stigler, G. (1961). The Economics of Information. *Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 69, pp. 213-225.
- [2] Robot-Neil MacMillan, River Allen, Dimitri Marinakis, Sue Whitesides, (2010). Range-based navigation system for a mobile. *IEEE* 2010.
- [3] Nolan Hergert, William Keyes, and Chao Wang, (2012). Smartphone-based Mobile Robot Navigation.
- [4] Phey Sia Kwek, Zhan Wei Siew, Chen How Wong, BihLiiChua, Kenneth Tze Kin Teo, (2012). Development of a Wireless Device Control Based Mobile Robot Navigation System. *IEEE* 2012.
- [5] Sebastian van D. & Andrew W. (2013). A Bluetooth-based Architecture for Android Communication with an Articulated Robot. *IEEE* 2013.